

PROFILING OF ANTI-SICKLING CONSTITUENTS OF OILY ISOLATE FROM N-HEXANE FRACTION OF *Telfairia Occidentalis* (FLUTED PUMPKIN) LEAVES EXTRACT USING GAS CHROMATOGRAPHY –MASS SPECTROMETRY

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DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.17769310

ABSTRACT

The *Telfairia occidentalis* plant is a widely used green vegetable and medicinal plant among Nigerians, valued for its nutritional and blood-boosting properties. This study investigated the profiling of antisickling constituents using gas chromatography-mass spectrometry (GC-MS). The antisickling activity was assessed using freshly prepared 2% sodium metabisulfite (negative control) and fractionated plant extracts (positive control) against hemoglobin SS red blood cells (HbSS). The n-hexane fraction exhibiting antisickling activity was selected for isolation through chromatographic techniques. Thin-layer chromatography (TLC) monitoring of the hexane fraction (first eluate) with a dichloromethane: methanol (9:1) solvent system yielded a pure, oily sample with a single spot, which was analyzed by GC-MS. Major components identified included 2-undecene (retention time (Rt): 4.864; 11.6%) and propenoic acid (Rt: 1.139; 3.9%), an unsaturated carboxylic acid. The percentage of sickling reduction by the hexane extract on Hb-SS erythrocytes demonstrated a dose-dependent effect, with reductions of 13.84% (125 µg/mL), 11.11% (250 µg/mL), and 2.84% (500 µg/mL), indicating significant antisickling activity.

Keywords: Antisickling activity, Gas Chromatography-Mass Spectrometry (GC-MS), *Telfairia occidentalis*, n-hexane, Haemoglobin.

1. INTRODUCTION

Sickle cell refers to a clinical abnormality that occurs when different genotypes affect the haemoglobin molecule. This is a genetic change that manifests when a neutral valine replaces the negatively charged glutamine at position 6 in both chains. This results in two fewer negative charges than normal haemoglobin Hb AA (Cyril-Olutayo *et al.*, 2019). The

inheritable disease, expressed in the homozygous state as haemoglobin S, causes a significant reduction in oxygen affinity and solubility. Other effects include cell polymerisation, high viscosity, prior deformability, depleted antioxidants, peroxidative membrane damage, and haemolysis (Atabo *et al.*, 2014).

The use of plants with medicinal properties has continued to play

protective and therapeutic roles, with documented histories. Herbal medicinal plants, because of their cost-effectiveness, availability, and accessibility, are of great importance in developing countries and can lead to the production of safer drugs.

Researchers have reported anti-sickling effects of many medicinal plants. Antisickling effects of many herbal plants, such as *Telfairia occidentalis* (Okoye *et al.*, 2024), *Aloe barbadensis*, *Bombax pentadrum*, *Carica papaya*, and others, have been reported (Iyekowa *et al.*, 2023). The therapeutic effect of this herbal plant is due to the synergistic effect of its constituents.

The *Telfairia occidentalis* leaves, despite their widespread use among patients with sickle cell disease (SCD), serve as a palliative in the management of sickle cell illness. It appears there is limited scientific investigation into developing effective and safer agents for SCD. The use of the n-hexane fraction of the leaves was selected following the antisickling assay and was supported by the work of Okoye *et al.* (2024).

2.0. METHODS AND MATERIALS

2.1. Equipment and Reagents.

Some equipment used included Vacuum liquid chromatography, Sephadex LH-20 column, rotary evaporator (R00010156, Cat No. Re300/MS, Baroworld Scientific Stone, Staffordshire), and GC-MS. All the solvents used in the analysis were re-distilled before use and of analytical grade.

2.2. Sample Collection and Preparation

Sample leaves of 1 kg from fluked pumpkin were collected from a vegetable farm in Awgbu, Orumba

North, Anambra State, Nigeria. This was done in February 2021. Mrs. Onwunyili Amaka performed the identification and authentication at the herbarium unit in the Department of Pharmacognosy, Faculty of Pharmaceutical Sciences, Nnamdi Azikiwe University, Awka. It was assigned voucher number PCG/474/A/026 after comparison with established herbarium specimens. The collected plant materials were separated from their twigs, air-dried for three weeks, and then ground into powder.

2.3 Extraction of Constituents Of The Leaves

A powdered leaf sample of *T. occidentalis* was extracted using a Soxhlet extractor with ethanol. 153g crude extract obtained with a rotary evaporator was concentrated and partitioned successively with solvents of increasing polarities as follows: n-hexane (4500 ml), ethyl acetate (2500 ml), butanol (1000 ml), and the parent ethanol extract to give four fractions. The fractions were evaluated for antisickling activity.

2.4 Qualitative screening for the antisickling compounds

2.4.1 Blood sample collection

Fresh blood samples and haemoglobin (Hb) type SS blood samples were collected from the haematology and blood transfusion department of Nnamdi Azikwe University Teaching Hospital, Nnewi (NAUTH), Nigeria.

2.4.2 Antisickling activity

The principle

The antisickling study was performed using the sodium metabisulphite (SMBS) test, modified from the method of Sofowora and Isaac-Sodeye (1979). It is based on the observation that red blood cells sickle under a microscope

when exposed to low oxygen tension. This method involves covering a drop of the blood sample mixed with a drop of sodium metabisulphite onto a clean glass slide. On gentle pressing of the slides, excess mixture was cleaned with tissue paper, and the edges were sealed adequately with petroleum jelly to exclude air. The reducing agent, sodium metabisulphite, acts by reducing oxyhaemoglobin to reducedhaemoglobin, thereby increasing sickling.

2.4.3 Antisickling Procedure

Stock solutions (500 µg, 250 µg, 125 µg) of the fractions (n-hexane, ethyl acetate, butanol, and aqueous phase) of the leaf extracts were prepared by dissolving 5 mg of each fraction in a beaker with 10 ml of phosphate buffer solution and mixing with a drop of freshly prepared 2% sodium metabisulfite. A 100 µl aliquot of the stock solution of the washed erythrocyte AA blood sample, which served as the positive control, was also prepared. All stock solutions were incubated for 2 hours. Ten-fold dilutions of the extract stock solutions in SS blood were then prepared. 10 µL of the control (2% sodium metabisulfite) and the extract doses were spotted on microscopical glass slides, and paraffin was applied to seal the edges of the cover completely to exclude air (hypoxia), then allowed to dry for several hours. Each slide was examined under an oil-immersion microscope at 10× magnification, and red blood cells were counted in three fields (×10, ×20, and ×40) on each slide (Iwu et al., 1988). The counts of both sickled and total blood cells were recorded, and the percentage of sickled cells was calculated using the formula:

2.4.4 Counting of cells:

(%) sickling = number of sickling cells × 100/total cells

2.5 Isolation and purification of antisickling compounds using different chromatographic techniques

A total of 53.92 g of the n-hexane fraction with the highest antisickling activity was subjected to vacuum liquid chromatography using four solvents, resulting in 22 fractions (TF22). The eluates were combined into 10 fractions based on TLC analyses. The solvent system was dichloromethane:methanol (9:1). The TF3 fraction, which showed the most significant antisickling activity, was further isolated by vacuum liquid chromatography, yielding 18 fractions. The oily isolate from fraction seven, labeled TF3-7A, was purified by elution from a multi-step liquid column chromatography column using Sephadex LH-20 with dichloromethane:methanol (5:5) as the solvent system. The oily extract was analyzed by GC-MS.

2.6 GC-MS Analysis

GC-MS analysis of the isolated oil (sample TF3-7A) from the n-hexane fraction of ethanol extract of *Telfiaria occidentalis* was performed using a Shimadzu GC-MS-QP2010SE. The oil was separated on an HP-5 MS (5.0% phenylsiloxane) column with nitrogen as the carrier gas at a flow rate of 1.80 ml/min. The oven program started at 70.0°C and held for 2 minutes, then ramped at 10.0°C/min to 280°C and maintained for 7 minutes. The sample was injected via an all-glass injector operating in split mode with a helium carrier gas flow rate of 1.2 ml/min. Identification of the chemical constituents relied on comparing retention times, fragmentation patterns, and mass spectra obtained by GC-MS. The retention indices, peak area percentages, and mass spectral fragmentation patterns from the chromatograms were compared with the NIST08 database of the National

Institute of Standards and Technology (NIST) to identify the compounds, including their names, molecular weights, formulas, and structures.

3.0. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1. Antisickling activity

From Table 1 below, there was a noticeable decrease in the percentage of sickle cells from 31.68% to 10% as the extract dose increased from 125 µg/mL to 250 µg/mL. However, at the highest extract dose, the percentage of non-sickle cells was 90%, indicating that the antisickling activity was dose-dependent. This result supports the findings of Njoku and Ejele (2004), which showed high reversal of sickled cells with the ethanol extract of *T.*

occidentalis. Their results demonstrated high hemoglobin production with fewer sickle cells among five volunteers with HbSS. The reversal of sickled cells was observed in this experiment with the use of hexane (a non-polar solvent) (Table 1), compared to the ethanol (polar solvent) extract reported by Njoku and Ejele (2004). This also supports the findings of Cyril-Olutayo *et al.*, (2019), who reported the highest reversal of sickled cells with ethanol extract of *T. occidentalis* leaves at a dose of 4 mg/mL. They observed a steady increase in antisickling activity from 1 mg/mL to 4 mg/mL for both inhibition and reversal activities.

Antisickling Activity

Table 1: Antisickling activity of hexane fraction of *T. occidentalis* on HbSS blood

Test sample	Number of sickle cell (%)	Number of non-sickle cell (%)
Hexane fraction (125 µg/mL)	12 (31.68)	26 (68.42)
Hexane fraction (250 µg/mL)	02 (10)	18(90)
Hexane fraction (500 µg/mL)	03 (10)	27 (90)
Control (10 µL)	17 (39.53)	26 (60,47)

Plate A: Optical micrograph of 500µg of n-hexane fraction of ethanol extract of *Telfairia occidentalis* on sickle cell blood at 2 hours (Magnification X10).

Plate B: Optical micrograph of 250 µg of ethyl acetate fraction of ethanol extract of *Telfairia occidentalis* on sickle cell blood at 2 hours (Magnification X10)

3.2. GC-MS Analysis

The GC-MS chromatogram of the isolated light yellow oil given in Figure 1 showed twenty (20) peaks, indicating from the search list of the Chemical

Abstract Service, twenty compounds. The chemical compounds identified in the oil fraction (according to the NIST Library) are presented in Table 2 below.

Figure 1: GC-MS chromatogram of TF3-7A isolated from *T. occidentalis*

Table 2: GC-MS Analysis of TF3-7A isolated from *T. occidentalis*

Peak	Retention time	Organic compound	Area (%)
1	1.139	Propenoic acid	3.90
2	4.864	2-undecene	11.6
3	5.726	Hexadecane	6.77
4	6.473	Octadecanol	5.67
5	7.677	Octanoic acid	6.02
6	7.946	1-Octadecanol	5.67
7	8.86	Formic acid	4.99
8	9.135	Succinic acid	5.33
9	9.29	Bicyclo[3.1.1]heptan-3-one	3.99
10	9.327	2-methyl octadecane	2.46
11	9.960	Pentanoic acid, decyl ester	3.90
12	10.058	1-Octen-3-ol	4.60
13	10.183	4-cyclohexene-1,2-dicarboxylic acid	4.99
14	10.520	4-hepten-3-one	4.24
15	11.049	Octasiloxane	2.87
16	11.127	Pentasiloxane	2.87
17	11.527	Hexanoic acid	3.21
18	11.656	Pyrocatechol	2.87
19	12.751	1,2-Cinnolindicarboxylic acid	3.90
20	12.953	Octasiloxane	2.12
TOTAL			100

The chemical constituents of the isolated compound TF3-7A from *T. occidentalis* indicated the presence of 20 different compounds. Detected compounds include 2-undecene (Retention time (Rt): 4.864, 11.60%), hexadecane (Rt: 5.726, 6.77%), and octanoic acid (Rt: 7.677, 6.02%) as the major components. While propenoic acid (Rt: 1.139: 3.90 %) and Bicyclo [3.1.1] heptan-3-one (Rt: 9.29: 3.99 %),

a terpenoid, were also implicated in the isolated fraction. These compounds have gained relevance over the years in the treatment of several diseases. Nopinone, which is bicycle [3.1.1] heptan-3-one, has been used to treat microbial infections. Studies have shown that nopinone derivatives possess antimicrobial properties (Liao *et al.*, 2015). In comparison, other applications include anticancer

potential (Wang *et al.*, 2017), among other pharmaceutical syntheses. Saturated carboxylic acids, such as formic acid and hexanoic acid, were also detected in the isolate, and their anti-inflammatory effects on cell

protection have been established. The unsaturated alkene, 2-undecene, has also shown antimicrobial, anti-inflammatory, antifungal, and antioxidant properties (Lee *et al.*, 2011)

Figure 2: Some chemical compounds of the GC-MS chromatogram detected from *Telfairia occidentalis* isolates (TF3-7A)

4.0. CONCLUSION

The study explores the oil profile of *Telfairia occidentalis* leaves and its antisickling potential in haemoglobin-SS erythrocytes. In the study, 2-undecene, hexadecane, and octanoic acid were identified as the major components. The oil constituents of the hexane extract exhibited a rich profile of bioactive compounds, while antisickling studies showed a dose-dependent reversal of sickle cells at graded concentrations.

CONFLICT OF INTEREST

The author declared no conflict of interest.

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